

An Investigation of Building Collapses in bangladesh

MD MOSFIKUR ROHAN(201880040141)
Civil department,zhengzhou university,

Introduction:

Every year a large number of buildings collapse around the world,in my view I saw this type of incident in my country,the largest disaster occurred on 24 April 2013 at Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh. rana plaza was the most pathatic tragedy in my country, there lots of poor people die and lots of People's injured so badly that cant be imagine, it was one of the biggest structure failure where 1,135 people were killed and 2,515 were injured,The Rana Plaza building was the establishment that had workers who were the commodity of the production of garments that are sold to the Western market

Review :

Buildings are structures that serve as shelters for man, his properties and activities.They must be properly planned, designed and constructed to obtain desired satisfaction from the environment. The factors to be observed in building construction include durability, adequate stability to prevent its failure or discomfort to the users, resistance to weather, fire outbreak and other forms of accidents.

When a building collapsed, devastating effects are felt more painfully by the inhabitants than the owner. Poor structural design, use of substandard building materials, non-compliance with approved building design, poor workmanship, and lack of qualified and cost control among others are the main causes of building failures in all over the world. Major structural failures of buildings around the world are currently well known to everyone because many are described in the print media. These failures become known to the public, because someone is killed or seriously hurt, not just to discredit the structural engineer, the builder and the other professionals involved in the case of the collapsed buildings. This research examines the cases of a collapsed building with special reference to Rana Plaza that was under construction in

Savar, Bangladesh. On 24 April 2013, Rana Plaza, an eight-storied commercial building, collapsed in Savar, a sub-district in the Greater Dhaka Area, the capital of Bangladesh. The search for the dead ended on 13 May with the death toll of 1,129. Around 2,515 victims were saved from the building alive. It is considered to be the deadliest garment-factory accident in history, as well as the deadliest accidental structural failure in modern human history. On Wednesday morning there was a power cut and diesel generators on the top floor were started. The building collapsed at about 08:57am leaving only the ground floor intact. The Bangladesh Garment Manufacturers and Exporters Association president confirmed that 3,122 workers were in the building at the time of the collapse. One local resident described the scene as if "an earthquake had struck."

Building Description :

The location of Rana Plaza Building was at Savar Bazar Bus stand, Savar, Dhaka. It was a ten storied building including one basement. It was Reinforced Cement Concrete Frame Structure 108 ft height above plinth. The Architecture and consultancy of Rana Plaza were done by Architects of Vaastukalpa (up to 5th Floor). The Structural Engineer was Engr. Sajjad Hossain, IEB M-1016380 and Rajuk E-00152. The building work was done by Sohel Rana owner of Rana Plaza. The opening year of Rana plaza was 2010 without complete it.

Approval of the Building:

The approval of the building was done by two stages. **In First Stage**, it was shown that the basement of the building was used for car parking, level 1 to 3 used as shops and 4 to 6 as office. There were two architectural drawing sheets containing floor plan, section and elevation. No structural drawings and soil investigation report were found in Pourashabha office. **In Second Stage**, it was shown that the basement of the building was used for car parking, level 1 to 3 used as shops and 4 to 10 as office. There were three architectural drawing sheets containing floor plan, section and elevation.

Construction and Quality Control:

There was no working structural drawing was available. Design concrete strength f_c and steel strength f_y was not specified in the submitted structural design. Brick chips were used as coarse aggregate. Test of construction materials (rebar, cement, concrete etc.) was never done. Work progress was never submitted to Pourashabha authority. The construction sequence/ method were faulty. There was absence of proper detailing.

HOUSING & BUILDING RESEARCH INSTITUTE
Building Materials Division
 Darus-Salam, Mirpur, Dhaka-1216

TEST REPORT

Sample	কক্ৰিট (সাতার বানা প্ৰাক্ৰাৰ ধৰ্মসংৰক্ষণ থেকে সংগ্ৰহকৃত)। (ASTM-C42)							
Source								
Memo/Ref. No.	05.41.2600.002.10.010.13-764				Date: 04-05-2013			
Sl. No.	Identification Mark	Date of Sample Collection	*Cylindrical Concrete Core Size (mm)	Date of Core Cutting	Date of Testing	Compressive Strength in (PSI)	Compressive Strength in (MPa)	Remarks
08.	Beam Level-2, M-1,3	09/05/2013	75 × 38	14/05/2013	14/05/2013	1515.25	10.45	
09.	Beam Level-2, M-1,3	09/05/2013	75 × 38	14/05/2013	14/05/2013	1597.90	11.02	
10.	Slab Level-3, I-1,2, J-1,2	09/05/2013	75 × 38	14/05/2013	14/05/2013	1270.20	8.76	
11.	Column Level-2, M-1	09/05/2013	75 × 38	14/05/2013	14/05/2013	1661.70	11.46	
12.	Column Level-2, M-1	09/05/2013	75 × 38	14/05/2013	14/05/2013	1468.85	10.13	
13.	Beam Level-3, K-1,3	09/05/2013	75 × 38	14/05/2013	14/05/2013	2131.50	14.70	
14.	Beam Level-3, K-1,2	09/05/2013	75 × 38	14/05/2013	14/05/2013	2059.00	14.20	

* Block sample collected from the field (Rana Plaza) and core cutting done in the laboratory.

Tested by:
 Md. Zakir Hossain
 Research Associate
 Housing & Building Research Institute
 Darus Salam Mirpur, Dhaka.

Verified by:
 (স্বাক্ষৰ কৰা হৈছে)
 (স্বাক্ষৰ কৰা হৈছে)
 (স্বাক্ষৰ কৰা হৈছে)
 (স্বাক্ষৰ কৰা হৈছে)

Section-in-Charge
 Senior Research Officer
 Physical Testing Research Laboratory
 Housing & Building Research Institute

Test Report for Tensile Strength of Reinforcement Bar of Rana Plaza

Sample	Deformed Bar (সাতার বানা প্ৰাক্ৰাৰ ধৰ্মসংৰক্ষণ থেকে সংগ্ৰহকৃত)। (ASTM A 370)							
Source								
Memo/Ref. No.	05.41.2600.002.10.010.13-764				Date: 04-05-2013			
Specimen No.	Date of Sample Collection	Identification Mark	Nominal dia in mm	Actual		Elongation (%) (Gauge length=203.2mm)	Yield Strength in (MPa)	Ultimate Tensile Strength in (MPa)
				Dia in mm	Area in cm ²			
1.	08/05/2013	Column, Level-4, M-2	22	21.80	3.73	7.50	323.14	461.63
2.	08/05/2013	Column, Level-4, M-2	22	21.82	3.74	12.50	321.30	459.00
3.	09/05/2013	Column, Level-2, M-2	22	21.75	3.72	17.50	328.41	469.16
4.	09/05/2013	Column, Level-2, M-2	22	21.80	3.73	13.75	329.56	470.81
5.	08/05/2013	Column, Level-4, M-2	22	21.82	3.74	12.50	321.30	459.00
6.	08/05/2013	Column, Level-2, M-2	22	21.75	3.72	17.50	328.41	469.16
7.	08/05/2013	Column, Level-2, M-2	22	21.80	3.73	13.75	329.56	470.81
8.	08/05/2013	Column, Level-3, D-6	20	18.75	2.76	18.75	275.52	393.60
9.	08/05/2013	Column, Level-3, D-6	20	18.90	2.81	6.25	262.19	374.55
10.	09/05/2013	Column, Level-1, N-1	16	15.80	1.96	5.12	425.59	607.91
11.	09/05/2013	Column, Level-1, N-1	16	15.70	1.94	12.50	456.98	652.86
12.	08/05/2013	Column, Level-3, N-1	16	15.85	1.97	13.20	352.34	530.46
13.	09/05/2013	Beam, Level-1, L-8,10	16	15.68	1.93	20.00	320.93	458.48
14.	09/05/2013	Beam, Level-1, L-8,10	16	15.68	1.93	25.00	343.86	458.48
15.	08/05/2013	Beam, Level-4, G-2,6	16	15.66	1.93	17.50	362.79	518.28

Test Report for Tensile Strength of Reinforcement Bar of Rana Plaza

Comparisons between Four Building Collapses:

The reason of **Ronan Point** collapse was initiated by improper maintenance of leaked gas pipes. The failure of the single panel caused one entire corner of the building to collapse because there was insufficient reinforcement steel passing between the panels and also the loads carried by the panel could not be redistributed to other adjacent panels, because there was no alternate route for the forces to follow. From all investigations it was seen that Ronan Point apartment tower was deeply flawed in both design and construction and in designing it, the existing building codes were not maintained appropriately.

In the investigation of **Hyatt Regency Walkway** collapse it was found that, the connection of rod hanger which carrying the 4th floor walkway pulled through the box beams was failed because the contractor modified the design detail to use 2 hanger rods instead of one and the engineer approved the design change without checking it. It was also seen that the nut of the box beam which supported the weight of 2 walkways instead of one.

The main reasons of Sampoong Department store collapse were poorly-laid foundation & unstable ground, substandard concrete mix with sea water and poor

reinforcement. In the designing of it, the required columns size was 80cm in diameter where 60 cm was used and the number of steel reinforcing bars into the concrete was 8, not the required 16. The another reason was the corruption and lack of supervision of Authorities.

Summary of Findings:

1. Building built on a filled-in pond which compromised structural integrity,
2. Conversion from commercial use to industrial use,
3. Addition of three floors above the original permit,
4. The use of substandard construction material (which led to an overload of the building structure aggravated by vibrations due to the generators). Those various elements indicated dubious business practices by Sohel Rana and dubious administrative practices in Sava

The building was never approvable. Because the name on the design of Engineer and Architect is not exists. There was no provision for verification and approval of structural design by approving authority (SavarPourashabha). Structural design was faulty and inadequate. The whole structural irregularity was due to faulty architectural design. The construction was done by the owner not engineered construction. There was no use of standard material. Also there were so many changes of occupancy by owner without design checking. Administrative failure was to prevent use of the building despite of getting advance signs and symptoms of collapse. Rana Plaza had some design inadequacy from the very beginning. The building was approved for two times and there were some faults during construction. From the ETABS analysis of Rana Plaza the energy diagram shows that the building was in danger position due to its static loads only. Some of the sections were needed to be stiffer by increasing the section. In a government investigation, it was shown that properties of concrete and other materials was much poor. Modulus of elasticity was near about 1500 ksi and for steel it varied for each and every section in a big scale.

Conclusion :

The main causes of failure of Hyatt Regency Walkway and Sampoong Department store were change of design without further checking of adequacy. In addition, the main causes of failure of Ronan Point and Twin Tower were the impact loads. From Rana plaza analysis by ETABS for static load we found that the structure was in danger position due to its static load only. So, it can be said that the preliminary crack was occurred due to static loads but the final failure was initiated by generator vibration. The building was stable for three years with these static loads because of its factor of safety.

